

IDENTIFYING BOTTLENECKS: UNVEILING FACTORS PROLONGING DOOR-TO-BALLOON TIME IN A PAKISTANI TERTIARY CARE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT

Dr Ayesha Saleem Khan^{*1}, Dr Syeda Sobya Owais², Dr Iqra Waseem³

¹PG Trainee Emergency Medicine, Shifa International Hospital Islamabad

²Consultant Emergency Medicine, Shifa international hospital Islamabad

³Dentist, The Consultants Place by Excel Labs

¹ayesha.s.khan55@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18311014>

Keywords

door-to-balloon time, ST segment elevation myocardial infarction, primary percutaneous coronary intervention, emergency department-related factors.

Article History

Received: 22 December 2024

Accepted: 03 January 2025

Published: 17 Feb 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr Ayesha Saleem Khan

Abstract

Objective: To assess the mean door-to-balloon time in patients with ST segment elevation myocardial infarction undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention and frequency of specific emergency department-related factors causing prolonged door-to-balloon (D2B) time.

Study design: Cross sectional study.

Study place and period: Shifa international hospital (Emergency department) Islamabad from 01 May 2024 to 31 October 2024.

Methodology: Two hundred and twenty patients were admitted from emergency and followed-up until their shifting to catheter lab for primary PCI using balloon inflation. The D2B time was noted. If D2B time was >90 minutes, then factors leading to prolonged D2B time were also noted including ECG interpretation, catheter lab activation, referred cases. Data will be collected using a proforma and analysed in SPSS ver. 27.0.

Results: The mean age of patients with STEMI was 51.05 ± 14.47 years. There were 134 (60.9%) male patients and 86 (39.1%) female patients with male-to-female ratio of 1.5: 1. The patients had symptoms of STEMI from mean duration of 10.65 ± 5.87 hours. The mean D2B time was observed to be 79.11 ± 22.86 min. Prolonged D2B time was noted in 77 (35%) cases. The major factor leading to prolonged D2B time was misdiagnosis that was noted in 25 (32.5%) cases, followed by catheter lab activation 23 (29.9%) and referred case 9 (11.7%).

Conclusion: According to findings of this study, the mean time for D2B in STEMI patients was less than 90 minutes, depicting that most of the STEMI patients undergo primary PCI within one to one and a half hour. This D2B time is acceptable and comparable to developed countries.

INTRODUCTION:

ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) is one of the most frequent presentation in emergency department which manifested as Acute coronary syndrome include chest pain, orthopnea, dyspnea, and left or right arm pain.¹

² Electrocardiogram (ECG) is gold standard investigation when it comes to evaluate a chest pain patient in emergency with or without risk

factors that can contribute to coronary artery disease.^{3,4} As soon as a STEMI is detected in the emergency room, the emergency physician's first goal is to expedite the patient's reperfusion therapy. For patients with STEMI, prompt reperfusion treatment is essential to reducing myocardial damage and enhancing prognoses. Removing the clot with primary PCI or

thrombolysis is the only effective therapy for coronary artery blockage.^{5,6}

The period between hospital arrival and balloon inflation during primary PCI is known as the "door-to-balloon" time, is a key performance indicator in STEMI care. Ideally this time should be 90 minutes and extended to 120 minutes in inter hospital transfer.^{7, 8} Late identification of patients experiencing chest discomfort, as well as delayed ECG, activation, and transfer to the catheterization laboratory, were the causes of the delays in one research.⁹ The intervention improved the total median D2B time and identified factors that might shorten the reperfusion therapy. It also demonstrated that simple and affordable operational processes can be changed to improve health care delivery.^{10, 11} Despite established guidelines, prolonged D2B time remain prevalent in several healthcare systems, especially in poor resource countries. The purpose of this study is to pinpoint the precise causes of extended D2B wait times in a cardiac center's emergency room. The literature provided inconsistent information about D2B time, and little effort has been made to pinpoint the causes of the extended time. Thus, the purpose of this study was to determine the magnitude for the local context. So that results can be implemented and improvements can be made in local settings improve the outcome of primary PCI.

METHODOLOGY:

After taking approval from the institutional review board (IRB letter number with dates), this Cross sectional study was carried out at the Shifa international hospital (Emergency department) Islamabad for around 6 months i.e. from 01 May 2024 to 31 October 2024. By using WHO calculator, sample size of 220 patients was estimated with 95% confidence level, $d=1$ and mean D2B time i.e. 60 ± 7.5 min in STEMI patients.¹² The patients who fulfilled following criteria were enrolled by using Non-probability sampling (Consecutive) technique.

Inclusion criteria: Patients aged 25-75 years, either gender, presenting with ECG criteria of STEMI. STEMI was noted as an abnormality detected on the 12-lead ECG, ≥ 2 mm elevation

in ST segment in 2 contiguous chest leads and ≥ 1 mm elevation in ST segment in 2 contiguous limb leads will be considered as significant. (8) Patients fall within the time window of Primary PCI were enrolled in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients presenting > 12 hours of onset of symptoms, undergoing repeat PCI or already had history of STEMI or NSTEMI, already received thrombolysis in current episode of STEMI or within last 6 months were excluded from the sample.

Informed consent was taken from attendants before enrolment. Demographics including name, age, gender, duration of symptoms, history of smoking, alcoholism, diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, time of presentation (during 24 hours), occupation, residence, socioeconomic status, were noted. Then patients were admitted in emergency wards and followed-up until their shifting to catheter lab for primary PCI using balloon inflation. The D2B time was noted. If D2B time was >90 minutes, then factors leading to prolonged D2B time were noted including ECG interpretation (misdiagnosis), catheter lab activation, and referral from other hospital (late admission). Data was collected using a pre-designed proforma.

All statistical analyses was done in SPSS ver. 27.0. Normality was assessed by Shapiro-Wilk test. Quantitative variables like age, duration of STEMI, D2B time were described as mean \pm SD. Categorical variables like gender, history of smoking, alcoholism, diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, factors leading to prolonged D2B time were expressed as frequency and percentage. Data was stratified for age, gender, duration of STEMI, residence, occupation, socioeconomic status, history of smoking, alcoholism, diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia and time of presentation (morning, night, evening, afternoon). Post-stratification, independent samples t-test was applied to compare mean D2B time in stratified groups and chi-square test for factors leading to prolonged D2B time in stratified groups. P-value at ≤ 0.05 was kept as significant.

RESULTS:

In this study, total 220 patients of STEMI were enrolled who fall in mean age of 51.05 ± 14.47 years. There were 134 (60.9%) male patients and 86 (39.1%) female patients with male-to-female ratio of 1.5: 1. The patients had symptoms of STEMI from mean duration of 10.65 ± 5.87 hours. There were more patients residing in urban areas 99 (45%) than semi-urban 66 (30%) or living in rural areas 55 (25%). There were very few farmers 16 (7.3%) who presented with STEMI, or retired persons 26 (11.8%), while majority was of housewives 69 (31.4%). There were more presentation of patients belong to middle class 94 (42.7%) than lower 84 (38.2%) or high class 42 (19.1%). This may be due to increase in sedentary lifestyle of individuals. Out of 220, there were 68 (30.9%) smokers, 40 (18.2%) alcoholic, 110 (50%) had diabetes mellitus, 135 (61.4%) had hypertension and 137 (62.3%) were found to have dyslipidemia on laboratory investigations. The most common time of presentation was night 43 (19.5%), followed by evening 41 (18.6%) and morning 37 (16.8%). About 33 (15.0%) presented in afternoon while 32 (14.5%) presented at midnight and 34 (15.5%) presented at dawn. The mean D2B time was observed to be 79.11 ± 22.86 min. Table-I

Prolonged D2B time was noted in 77 (35%) cases. Figure-1

The major factor leading to prolonged D2B time was misdiagnosis that was noted in 25 (32.5%)

cases, followed by catheter lab activation 23 (29.9%) and referred case 9 (11.7%) in whom careful investigation, clinical examination and decision need to be made by presenting emergency cardiologist. Figure-2

We split data in different groups of effect modifiers including age, gender, residence, socioeconomic class, duration of STEMI and time of one 24-hour day at presentation. We observed that there is no impact of age on mean D2B time and mean D2B time in patients aged 25-50 years was 78.08 ± 23.52 min while of patients aged 51-75 years was 79.98 ± 22.34 min ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, there is no impact of gender on mean D2B time and mean D2B time of male patients was 79.60 ± 22.30 while of female patients was 78.34 ± 23.81 min ($p > 0.05$). The mean D2B time of patients who had STEMI from ≤ 12 hours was 80.50 ± 23.50 min and for patients who had STEMI from > 12 hours was 77.06 ± 21.84 min ($p > 0.05$). Residence, socioeconomic status and time of presentation also had no impact on mean D2B time ($p > 0.05$). Table-II

Similarly, for prolonged D2B time, age, gender, duration of STEMI had no significant impact ($p > 0.05$). All patients had equal chance of prolonged or early D2B time. Residence, socioeconomic status and time of presentation also had no impact on mean D2B time ($p > 0.05$). Table-IV

Table-I: Basic demographic profile of enrolled cases (n = 220)

Profile	F (%)
n	220
Age	51.05 ± 14.47 years
Gender	
Male	134 (60.9%)
Female	86 (39.1%)
Duration of STEMI	10.65 ± 5.87 hours
Residence	
Rural	55 (25%)
Urban	99 (45%)
Semi-urban	66 (30%)
Occupation	
Job	59 (26.8%)
Business	50 (22.7%)
Farmer	16 (7.3%)
Retired	26 (11.8%)

Housewife	69 (31.4%)
Socioeconomic status	
Low	84 (38.2%)
Middle	94 (42.7%)
High	42 (19.1%)
History of	
Smoking	68 (30.9%)
Alcoholism	40 (18.2%)
Diabetes mellitus	110 (50%)
Hypertension	135 (61.4%)
Dyslipidemia	137 (62.3%)
Time at presentation	
Morning	37 (16.8%)
Night	43 (19.5%)
Evening	41 (18.6%)
Afternoon	33 (15.0%)
Midnight	32 (14.5%)
Dawn	34 (15.5%)
D2B time	79.11 ± 22.86 min

Figure-I: showing prolonged D2B time

Figure-II: factors leading to prolonged D2B time (n = 77)

Table-II: Comparison of different groups of patients for mean D2B time when controlled for effect modifiers (n = 220)

		N	Mean	p-value
Age	25-50 years	101	78.08 ± 23.52	0.539
	51-75 years	119	79.98 ± 22.34	
Sex	Male	134	79.60 ± 22.30	0.689
	Female	86	78.34 ± 23.81	
Duration of STEMI	<12 hours	131	80.50 ± 23.50	0.273
	>12 hours	89	77.06 ± 21.84	
Residence	Rural	55	77.85 ± 22.05	0.804
	Urban	99	78.85 ± 23.64	
	Semi-urban	66	80.55 ± 22.59	
Socioeconomic status	Low	84	81.89 ± 24.20	0.264
	Middle	94	76.33 ± 22.00	
	High	42	79.76 ± 21.75	
Time of presentation	Morning	37	79.59 ± 24.06	0.982
	Night	43	78.49 ± 24.55	
	Evening	41	80.46 ± 22.88	
	Afternoon	33	80.21 ± 21.28	
	Midnight	32	79.31 ± 24.27	

Table-IV: Association of prolonged D2B time with effect modifiers (n = 220)

		Prolonged time		p-value
		Yes n=77	No n=143	
Age	25-50 years	34 (33.7%)	67 (66.3%)	0.702
	51-75 years	43 (36.1%)	76 (63.9%)	
Gender	Male	47 (35.1%)	87 (64.9%)	0.977
	Female	30 (34.9%)	56 (65.1%)	

Duration of STEMI	≤12 hours	49 (37.4%)	82 (62.6%)	0.364
	>12 hours	28 (31.5%)	61 (68.5%)	
Residence	Rural	16 (29.1%)	39 (70.9%)	0.391
	Urban	34 (34.3%)	65 (65.7%)	
	Semi-urban	27 (40.9%)	39 (59.1%)	
Socioeconomic status	Low	34 (40.5%)	50 (59.5%)	0.361
	Middle	31 (33.0%)	63 (67.0%)	
	High	12 (28.6%)	30 (71.4%)	
Time of presentation with STEMI	Morning	12 (32.4%)	25 (67.6%)	0.831
	Night	15 (34.9%)	28 (65.1%)	
	Evening	15 (36.6%)	26 (63.4%)	
	Afternoon	14 (42.4%)	19 (57.6%)	
	Midnight	12 (37.5%)	20 (62.5%)	
	Dawn	9 (26.5%)	25 (73.5%)	

DISCUSSION:

In our study, we observed the mean D2B time was observed to be 79.11 ± 22.86 min. Prolonged D2B time was noted in 77 (35%) cases. The major factor leading to prolonged D2B time was misdiagnosis that was noted in 25 (32.5%) cases, followed by catheter lab activation 23 (29.9%) and referred case 9 (11.7%).

In a study of 354 STEMI patients, Butt et al., found that over 85% of patients who received PCI had a D2B time of less than 90 minutes. Between 2010 and 2018, the median D2B time was 79 (IQR=31) minutes. They came to the conclusion that when the key players work together to provide patient-centered care, STEMI patients can reach the global standard of D2B time within 90 minutes.¹³ Another study by Khowaja et al., found that the median time for STEMI patients was 60±7.5 minutes.¹² The median D2B time, according to Champasri et al., was 54 (range=24-90) minutes, and there was a notable difference in STEI patients who were referred from other clinical centers (44 minutes, IQR: 25-77) and those who arrived at the hospital directly (81 minutes, IQR: 56-129).¹⁴ In a study of 363 STEMI patients receiving primary PCI, Emani et al., found that the most common causes of D2B time delays were misdiagnosis (24.8%) and catheterisation lab use (26.2%). Additional indicators included non-STEMI on presenting ECG in 13.8% and referrals from other institutions in 11.0%.¹⁵

The STEMI patients are transported around-the-clock by the emergency medical service. When they first come into contact with patients at

home, trained emergency medical service technicians take their ECGs. After a cardiologist confirms myocardial infarction, the patient is moved to a local PCI facility. Patients are admitted to the catheterisation lab after arriving at the hospital without being admitted to the emergency room, reducing prehospital and hospital delays. The importance of emergency medical service transfers in avoiding delays has been shown in a number of studies.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

According to other relevant data, women are more likely than males to experience D2B time delays.^{19, 20} Nonetheless, women made up one-fourth of our patients with D2B delays. A Portuguese study found that women did not report more delays than men, which is consistent with our findings.¹⁶ In our study, we also did not find any significant impact of gender on delay of D2B time and observed that the time was almost similar i.e. 79.60 ± 22.30 min for males and 78.34 ± 23.81 min for females (p>0.05).

Additionally, 11.0% of patients with extended D2B times were referred from other hospitals, according to Emami et al.¹⁵ This frequency is almost similar as we observed in our study (11.7%). Referrals are linked to longer D2B times, according to a Korean study.^{18, 21} It is advised that STEMI patients who are referred from other hospitals be quickly transferred to the catheterisation laboratory without having to repeat diagnostic procedures in the emergency room. Additionally, a number of studies have shown that getting patient consent prolongs the D2B period, especially in Asian nations like India and China.²² Due to consent, only 2.5%

of patients postponed main PCI. Based on this logic, a recent study proposed eliminating the permission requirement.²³

Hsiao et al., investigated into the connection between a patient's arrival time and their D2B time as well as other D2B time segments. About 327 of the 732 STEMI patients arrived during the day (08:01–16:00), 268 in the evening (16:01–24:00), and 137 at night (00:01–08:00). The probability of prolonged D2B time was significantly more at night-time than daytime (adjusted OR: 2.87; 95% CI: 1.50–5.51, $p = 0.002$). The primary cause of this delay was a delay in the activation-to-arrival time of the cardiac catheter laboratory (adjusted OR: 6.25; 95% CI: 3.75–10.40, $p < 0.001$), especially between 00:00 and 04:00.²⁴

However, in a study involving 109 STEMI patients, Amoras et al. found that the D2B time was 104 minutes, and that 62.4% of the cases had a protracted D2B period. They determined that the D2B time was longer than advised after reporting the highest D2B time. The main PCI was delayed due to door-to-ECG time and ECG-to-activation time.²⁵

In a related study, Dhungel et al. found that the median D2B time was 79 (IQR: 59–115) minutes. The D2B time was <90 minutes observed in 58.2% patients. There was significant difference in D2B time between direct visit and referral ($p=0.029$) and between office or day timings (9–5 pm) and off or night timings (5–9 am) ($p=0.012$). Age ($p=0.330$), gender ($p=0.254$), diabetes ($p=0.487$) and hypertension ($p=0.073$), did not show any significant differences. These findings were comparable to the findings of our study. We also observed that there is no impact of any effect modifier including age, gender, duration of STEMI or residence (distance from hospital) or socioeconomic status on D2B time prolongation.²⁶

Throughout the investigation, we also noticed a few restrictions. Due to the fact that this research was based on observational data, a few factors were not evaluated throughout the study, but they could have an impact on the results. Although we used rigorous risk adjustment to try to lessen this impact, we cannot completely rule out the possibility of residual confounding caused by other non-assessed hospital variables

related to the D2B time or death in other non-assessed individuals.

CONCLUSION:

According to findings of this study, the mean time for D2B in STEMI patients was <90 minutes, depicting that most of the STEMI patients undergo primary PCI within one to one and a half hour. This D2B time is acceptable and comparable to developed countries. These results indicated that there is a need for monitoring the time factors of D2B time for better management of patients with STEMI, in order to reduce the hindrances to timely coronary intervention by primary PCI.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

None.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

REFERENCES:

- Yan F, Zhang Y, Pan Y, Li S, Yang M, Wang Y, et al. Prevalence and associated factors of mortality after percutaneous coronary intervention for adult patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Medical Sciences* 2023;28(1):17.
- Zuccarelli V, Andreaggi S, Walsh JL, Kotronias RA, Chu M, Vibhishanan J, et al. Treatment and care of patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction—what challenges remain after three decades of primary percutaneous coronary intervention? *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 2024;13(10):2923.
- Teo KK, Rafiq T. Cardiovascular risk factors and prevention: a perspective from developing countries. *Canadian Journal of Cardiology* 2021;37(5):733-43.
- Mattu A, Tabas JA, Brady WJ. *Electrocardiography in emergency, acute, and critical care*. New York: American College of Emergency Physicians; 2019.

- Alyamani M, Campbell S, Navarese E, Welsh RC, Bainey KR. Safety and efficacy of intracoronary thrombolysis as adjunctive therapy to primary PCI in STEMI: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Canadian Journal of Cardiology* 2021;37(2):339-46.
- Kalra S, Bhatt H, Kirtane AJ. Stenting in primary percutaneous coronary intervention for acute ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction. *Methodist DeBakey cardiovascular journal* 2018;14(1):14.
- O'Gara PT, Kushner FG, Ascheim DD, Casey DE, Chung MK, De Lemos JA, et al. 2013 ACCF/AHA guideline for the management of ST-elevation myocardial infarction: a report of the American College of Cardiology Foundation/American Heart Association Task Force on Practice Guidelines. *Journal of the American college of cardiology* 2013;61(4):e78-e140.
- Al-Rumhi MAS. Risk Factors and Outcomes Associated With Door-To-Balloon Time Among Patients With ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction in Oman. Oman: Sultan Qaboos University (Oman); 2021.
- Al Bugami S, Alrahimi J, Almalki A, Alamger F, Krimly A, Al Kashkari W. St-Segment elevation myocardial infarction: door-to-balloon time improvement project. *Cardiology Research* 2016;7(4):152.
- Zeng X, Chen L, Chandra A, Zhao L, Ma G, Roldan FJ, et al. Narrative review: updates and strategies for reducing door-to-balloon time in ST-elevation myocardial infarction care. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine* 2025;12:1509365.
- LEE CH, Ooi SB, Tay EL, Low AF, TEO SG, Lau C, et al. Shortening of median door-to-balloon time in primary percutaneous coronary intervention in Singapore by simple and inexpensive operational measures: clinical practice improvement program. *Journal of Interventional Cardiology* 2008;21(5):414-23.
- Khowaja S, Ahmed S, Kumar R, Shah JA, Khan KA, Khan NU, et al. Time to think beyond door-to-balloon time: significance of total ischemic time in STEMI. *The Egyptian Heart Journal* 2021;73(1):95.
- Butt TS, Bashtawi E, Bououn B, Wagley B, Albarrak B, Sergani HE, et al. Door-to-balloon time in the treatment of ST segment elevation myocardial infarction in a tertiary care center in Saudi Arabia. *Annals of Saudi medicine* 2020;40(4):281-9.
- Champasri K, Srimahachota S, Chandavimol M, Udayachalerm W, Thakkinstian A, Sookananchai B, et al. Door-to-device time and mortality in patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction treated with primary percutaneous coronary intervention: insight from real world data of Thai PCI Registry. *Cardiovascular Diagnosis and Therapy* 2023;13(5):843-54.
- Emami M, Mirzamohamadi S, Heidari A, Aein A, Salarifar M, Nematipour E. Evaluation of the Causes of Door-to-Balloon Time Delays in Patients with ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction at Tehran Heart Center. *The journal of Tehran Heart Center* 2023;18(1):68-71.
- Pereira H, Cale R, Pinto FJ, Pereira E, Caldeira D, Mello S, et al. Factors influencing patient delay before primary percutaneous coronary intervention in ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction: The Stent for life initiative in Portugal. *Revista Portuguesa de Cardiologia (English Edition)* 2018;37(5):409-21.
- Ericsson M, Thylén I, Strömberg A, Ängerud KH, Moser DK, Sederholm Lawesson S. Factors associated with patient decision time in ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction, in early and late responders—an observational cross-sectional survey study. *European Journal of Cardiovascular Nursing* 2022;21(7):694-701.

- Shi O, Khan AM, Rezaei MR, Jackevicius CA, Cox J, Atzema CL, et al. Factors associated with door-in to door-out delays among ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) patients transferred for primary percutaneous coronary intervention: a population-based cohort study in Ontario, Canada. *BMC Cardiovascular Disorders* 2018;18(1):204.
- Sim WJ, Ang AS, Tan MC, Xiang WW, Foo D, Loh KK, et al. Causes of delay in door-to-balloon time in south-east Asian patients undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention. *PLoS One* 2017;12(9):e0185186.
- Babiolakis CS, Sharma S, Sayed N, Abunassar JG, Haseeb S, Abuzeid W. The effect of sex on door-to-balloon time in patients presenting with ST-elevation myocardial infarction and referred for primary percutaneous coronary intervention: a systematic review. *Cardiovascular Revascularization Medicine* 2022;37:120-7.
- Park JH, Ahn KO, Do Shin S, Cha WC, Ryoo HW, Ro YS, et al. The first-door-to-balloon time delay in STEMI patients undergoing interhospital transfer. *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine* 2016;34(5):767-71.
- Li L, Wu M-Y, Zhang F, Li S-F, Cui Y-X, Hu D, et al. Perspective of delay in door-to-balloon time among Asian population. *Journal of Geriatric Cardiology: JGC* 2018;15(12):732.
- Ravi M, Abraham SV, Palatty BU, Balakrishnan JM. Door-to-balloon time in patients presenting with acute ST elevation myocardial infarction and time factors influencing it; an observational study from a tertiary care teaching hospital in India. *Indian Heart Journal* 2021;73(3):359-61.
- Hsiao Y-T, Hung J-F, Zhang S-Q, Yeh Y-N, Tsai M-J. The impact of emergency department arrival time on door-to-balloon time in patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction receiving primary percutaneous coronary intervention. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 2023;12(6):2392.
- Amoras TSG, Rodrigues TB, Menezes CR, Zaninotto CV, Tavares RdS. Door-to-balloon Time in Cardiovascular Emergency Care in a Hospital of Northern Brazil. *International Journal of Cardiovascular Sciences* 2020;34(1):53-9.
- Dhungel S, Malla R, Adhikari C, Maskey A, Rajbhandari R, Sharma R, et al. Door-to-balloon time and the determining factors in a tertiary cardiac center in Nepal. *Indian heart journal* 2018;70:S309-S12.